

The Metaverse Context Analysis

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Abstract

Abstract: *The report The Metaverse Context Analysis provides a preliminary examination of the context and dynamics of the Metaverse, offering a foundation for understanding the enabling technologies and analytical categories relevant to exploring the social and cultural implications of this rapidly evolving virtual space. This work aligns with the objectives outlined in Milestone A1.1 of the MetaJust project. The document addresses key aspects, including the debate surrounding the definition of the Metaverse, its historical-technological reconstruction, and exploratory developments in governance, with particular emphasis on the role of decentralisation goals underpinned by the advancement of blockchain technologies and the use of cryptocurrencies. Finally, the report identifies examples of public services implemented through Metaverse technologies, which will be further analysed to understand better the opportunities and challenges posed by this evolving virtual ecosystem.*

1. Introduction

The contemporary collective imagination surrounding the Metaverse has been profoundly shaped by the visual representations provided by literature, cinema, and video games. These media have contributed to developing the idea of an immersive environment with a futuristic and science-fiction character. This vision finds its roots in Neal Stephenson’s post-cyberpunk novel *Snow Crash*, published in 1992. Set against a dystopian backdrop, the Metaverse in the story emerges as a virtual refuge from economic oppression, a place where desires and aspirations can be realised—allowing an ordinary delivery driver to reinvent himself as a master swordsman.

The image of the Metaverse portrayed in *Snow Crash*¹ remains strikingly relevant even after thirty years of technological advancements. In the novel, Stephenson accurately anticipates many features now associated with the Metaverse, describing it as a digital space accessible via virtual reality devices, such as headsets, enabling users to immerse themselves in a shared virtual environment. Within this space, individuals interact through graphical representations of themselves, known as avatars. This vision not only shaped the concept of the Metaverse but also prefigured its technological framework and the imagination of a three-dimensional virtual space where identity and social interactions take on new forms.

In addition to describing enabling technologies and foundational principles—such as the criteria of continuity and coherence within virtual universes—Stephenson’s Metaverse presents an

¹ Stephenson, N. (1992). *Snow Crash*. Bantam Books.

idealised vision of this digital realm. It is portrayed as a space of escapism and utopia, where dreams, aspirations, and fantasies, unattainable in the physical world, find a place to thrive.

This liberating aspiration was echoed in the 2021 announcement by Facebook CEO Mark Zuckerberg regarding the company's rebranding as Meta, marking the beginning of a focused investment phase aimed at creating the Metaverse. In the statement *Introducing Meta: A Social Technology Company*², the company articulated its vision to bring the Metaverse to life, describing it as a hybrid of online social experiences expanded into three dimensions or projected into the physical world, "allowing you to do things you couldn't do in the physical world". The Metaverse was presented as the next chapter of the internet and social media, with its defining quality being the removal of the screen's limitation to create a sense of presence³. This conceptual shift framed the Metaverse not merely as a technological innovation but as a transformative medium redefining the way users engage with digital and physical realities.

From its introduction into the collective imagination in 1992 to the revolution promised by Zuckerberg in 2021, the concept of the Metaverse has undergone a long journey marked by technological innovations, definitional debates, governance architectures, and regulatory proposals. These evolving and expanding trajectories have shaped the notion of the Metaverse as «the next generation of the Internet in which the users, as avatars, can interact with each other and software applications in a three-dimensional (3D) virtual space» (Duan *et al.*, 2021:para. 1)⁴.

In the following pages, we will explore the concept of the Metaverse and its evolution, analysing the various existing definitions and their interplay with enabling technologies to understand its social impacts. The aim is to examine how its architecture, including governance frameworks, fits within the broader trajectory of digital realities' development and its implementation in the fields of justice and public administration.

2. The Metaverse' origins: a contemporary debate

The transition of Facebook into Meta is part of a broader context of renewed interest in immersive and virtual realities among major technology and hardware market players. This enthusiasm has been fuelled by narratives framing this surge in investment as the "new internet

² Meta. (2021, October 28). *Facebook company is now Meta*.

<https://about.fb.com/news/2021/10/facebook-company-is-now-meta/> [Accessed: 12 November 2024].

³ Zuckerberg, M. (2021, October 28). *Founder's letter*. <https://about.fb.com/news/2021/10/founders-letter> [Accessed: 12 November 2024].

⁴ Duan, H., Li, J., Fan, S., Lin, Z., Wu, X., & Cai, W. (2021, October). Metaverse for social good: A university campus prototype. In *Proceedings of the 29th ACM International Conference on multimedia* (pp. 153-161).

revolution” (see Ball 2022⁵; van Rijmenam 2022⁶; Marr 2023)⁷. However, within the academic and scientific spheres, there is little consensus regarding analyses of the Metaverse’s development—both historical and contemporary—or its technological and governance characteristics.

Contrary to the narrative promoted by major industry players, some argue that the Metaverse is not merely a forward-looking phenomenon; its roots extend into the past, with cultural and technological references dating back to the early days of virtual reality and digital networks. One of the precursors to the Metaverse can be traced to the text-based interactive games of the 1970s. These digital play spaces allowed players to communicate in real-time via text and collaborate in gameplay (Duan et al., 2021, para. 4.1.1). These text-based games paved the way for 3D virtual worlds, where users could enter as digital representations, or avatars, and interact not only through text but also through voice, enriching the virtual experience (Duan et al., 2021). Both forms of digital spaces charted the path toward the contemporary Metaverse, bridging multiplayer gaming environments and decentralised virtual worlds.

Researchers who validate a view of the Metaverse not solely oriented toward the future often identify three waves of its development. The first wave refers to technologies such as flight simulators from the 1920s, immersive and multisensory theatres of the 1950s, and video games of the 1970s. These innovations created «a sense of an alternative reality for the user. However, users could not interact with the virtual objects» (Dolata & Schwable 2023:241)⁸. The second wave is marked by the rapid proliferation of multiplayer online games in the late 2000s. This growth was driven by technological advancements that made 3D technologies and home computers more accessible, bringing these innovations to a broader audience. Finally, the third and most recent wave of the Metaverse is identified with contemporary technological transformations, including the widespread adoption of portable computers and hardware devices, artificial intelligence, and other enabling technologies.

From this perspective, the Metaverse is not merely the culmination of contemporary technological advancements but predates many of the technologies now considered integral to its existence. This shift in viewpoint invites us to examine the Metaverse not only as the sum and evolution of its constituent technologies and their idealised future but also in terms of the governance, participation, and user experiences that define its essence.

⁵ Ball, M. (2022). *The Metaverse: And How It Will Revolutionize Everything*. Liveright Publishing Corporation.

⁶ Van Rijmenam, M. (2022). *Step into the Metaverse: How the Immersive Internet Will Unlock a Trillion-Dollar Social Economy*. Wiley.

⁷ Marr, B. (2023). *The Future Internet: How the Metaverse, Web 3.0, and Blockchain Will Transform Business and Society*. John Wiley & Sons.

⁸ Dolata, M; Schwable, G. (2023). What is the Metaverse and who seeks to define it? Mapping the site of social construction. *Journal of Information Technology*. Vol. 38(3) 239-166.

As Arcagni (2023)⁹ explains, the Metaverse is not just the new technological frontier announced by Meta, Apple, Microsoft, and other high-tech companies. These corporations have appropriated a term that has circulated for decades, redefining and branding it to align with their immersive technology sectors, such as virtual and augmented reality. What we are witnessing is the evolution of a concept with a long history of experimentation, proposals, and technological applications rooted in the world of video games. For some observers, the Metaverse is, in certain respects, reshaping the cultural landscape of modern technologies (Arcagni 2023).

The aim, therefore, is to analyse the concept of the Metaverse not solely from a technological perspective but also through cultural and sociological lenses, distancing it from the dominant narrative promoted by major investors (Arcagni 2023). This approach allows for an exploration of whether and how the Metaverse truly represents a breakthrough—a “revolution”—in the current structures of digital media, highlighting its potential and challenges for society.

3. The debate on the definition

From the complex context outlined above, it is easy to infer that, alongside the historical debate, there is still no clear and widely accepted definition of the Metaverse. This uncertainty reflects the multiple interests at stake, as the definition itself results from a confrontation between different perspectives and priorities. Discussions about the Metaverse, including the various proposed definitions in circulation, must be analysed by considering the conditions of existence that determine them, namely the set of rules and principles that constitute the historical, political, and economic context in which they are embedded (Foucault 1969)¹⁰. Defining the Metaverse should not, therefore, be regarded as a neutral act but as a controversial process responding to the interests and orientations of the individuals working on a given proposal, who are themselves situated within historically and politically located dynamics and processes. Understanding this aspect requires going beyond a definition that only describes the technical and technological components to embrace a critical analysis of the interests involved, the goals and practices associated with the concept of the “Metaverse,” and the role it could play within society.

Definitions of the Metaverse vary both historically and conceptually: some describe it as a space, place, or world (emphasising the physical dimension), while others conceive it as a system, network, medium, or simulation, focusing more on internal interactions and external connections

⁹ Arcagni, S. (2023). *La zona oscura. Filosofia del Metaverso* [The Dark Zone: Philosophy of the Metaverse]. Luiss University Press.

¹⁰ Foucault, M. (1969). *The Archaeology of Knowledge* (5th ed., G. Bogliolo, Trans.). Milan: RCS Libri & Grandi Opere.

(Dolata, Schwable 2023; Park, Kim 2022¹¹). The proposals also differ regarding the technologies and characteristics that should define the Metaverse. According to the authors of the paper, *What is the Metaverse and who seeks to define it? Mapping the site of social construction* (Dolata, Schwable 2023), a challenging element of the debate on its definition is that «most papers presuppose that the Metaverse can be objectively defined in terms of its nature or constituents and that there is (or should be) a single, valid definition. This assumption is problematic because it sees technology as static and unlikely to change, whereas the meanings attached to technologies were shown to emerge and shift over time» (Dolata, Schwable 2023:242). In line with the authors of the paper, the idea is that «what the Metaverse is and will become relies on the collective sensemaking processes' outcomes» (Dolata, Schwable 2023:242). In these processes of meaning-making regarding the investments and evolution of the Metaverse, on the one hand, definitions emerge that fuel the idea of a constantly evolving Metaverse, presented as the product of a technological revolution, even before a social one. In this context, the focus is often placed on the technologies and devices that enable its usage. On the other hand, some adopt a more sceptical stance, anchoring the analysis to the current governance architecture of the web and questioning the actual realisation of the transformations promised by the Metaverse. The major players in the technology sector often promote the narrative that emphasises the Metaverse as a constantly evolving entity and a revolutionary technological phenomenon: the practical realisation of a science fiction future painted by cinema and literature. In contrast, social researchers tend to favour a more critical and analytical approach, focusing on the structural, social, and political aspects that characterise the ongoing digital transformations.

The *Centre on Regulation in Europe* (CERRE), in a report published in February 2024, clearly identifies the tendency to equate the definition of the Metaverse with the sum of its enabling technological components. The outcome of this overlap leads to the awareness that, at the current stage of technological development, the use of the term Metaverse is not appropriate (Di Porto, Fòà, Ennis 2024)¹². Through a survey and comparison of some definitions proposed by European and US international institutions with those emerging from the academic environment, the authors note that the different definitions of the Metaverse describe the future outcome of a technological development process originating in contemporary virtual worlds¹³. This evolution places the Metaverse in achieving full interconnection, interoperability, and decentralisation of different virtual worlds. Currently, these virtual worlds are fundamentally isolated from one another, each designed to offer specific user experiences and characterised by various levels of immersivity, synchronisation, and persistence (Di Porto, Fòà, Ennis 2024). Virtual worlds are thus not considered equivalent to the Metaverse but rather a precursor to it, which can only be

¹¹ Park, S. M.; Kim, Y. G. (2022). A Metaverse: taxonomy, components, applications, and open challenges. *IEEE Access* 10: 4209–4251.

¹² Di Porto, F; Fòà, D.; Ennis, S. (2024). *Emerging virtual worlds: Implications for policy and regulation*. Centre on Regulation in Europe (CERRE).

¹³ According to the authors of the CERRE report, virtual worlds can be defined as «an immersive, synchronous, persistent and unified 3D user experience that enables mass content creation» (Di Porto, Fòà, Ennis 2024:14).

appropriately defined as such when interoperability and decentralisation allow for the creation of a network of interconnected virtual worlds (Di Porto, Fòa, Ennis 2024).

This framework closely mirrors the definition offered by Matthew Ball (2022) and echoed in a report by the Metaverse Observatory, according to which the Metaverse is a large-scale, interoperable network of real-time, three-dimensional virtual worlds that can be experienced synchronously and persistently by an unlimited number of users with an individual sense of presence, and continuity of data, such as identity, history, rights, objects, communications, and payments. As previously discussed, this definition does not reflect the current technological capabilities and once again projects the Metaverse into a future dimension, in line with narratives foreseeing a technological revolution of the web. Similarly, the *Extended Reality and Metaverse Observatory* at the Politecnico di Milano defines the Metaverse as an «immersive, persistent, interactive, synchronous, and interoperable ecosystem of virtual worlds that can also be connected with the physical world, where users have the opportunity to replicate or enhance their activities and create and own assets, also accessing and using Extended Reality technologies» (Osservatorio Extended Reality & Metaverse 2024:11)¹⁴.

As previously noted, this vision is not widely shared, and according to some authors, «retrospectively, the text-based interactive games, such as MUD (multi-user dungeon) that emerged in the late 1970s, could be viewed as the earliest prototypes of Metaverse [...]. They define a multiplayer virtual world with role-playing, interactive fiction, and online chat» (Cheng *et al.*, 2022:1)¹⁵. According to these authors, the current development of technologies such as augmented reality, virtual reality, and mixed reality allows for a new consideration of the Metaverse, more aligned with the idea of a collection of 3D virtual worlds connected via the internet focused on social interaction, but not necessarily pioneering (Cheng *et al.* 2022).

Some interesting insights that seem to coherently frame the idea of the Metaverse within the current political and economic structures and dynamics are proposed by Jon M. Garon (2022) in the essay *Legal Implications of Ubiquitous Metaverse*¹⁶. The author argues that both today and in the future, it is not appropriate to talk about a single Metaverse but rather multiple Metaverses (or multiverses), namely, «a loose confederation of distinct virtual worlds and metaverse environments. The multiverse will be an international, partially interoperable array of metaverses, each subject to a different mix of state authority, corporate oversight, and participatory governance» (Garon 2022:7). The reasons for rejecting the idea of a unified Metaverse, replacing it with the development of different metaverse spaces, follow a series of considerations. First, the variety of regulatory contexts within which virtual environments operate will promote the development of potentially very diverse experiences across different

¹⁴ Osservatorio Extended Reality & Metaverse (Aprile 2024). *Esperienze Immersive tra fisico e digitale: back to reality*.

¹⁵ Cheng, R., Wu, N., Chen, S., & Han, B. (2022). Will metaverse be next internet? vision, hype, and reality. *IEEE network*, 36(5), 197-204.

¹⁶ Garon, J. M. (2022). Legal implications of a ubiquitous metaverse and a Web3 future. *Marq. L. Rev.*, 106, 163.

nations. Secondly, a central element identified in the revolution promoted by the Metaverse is the overcoming of the current digital system towards a decentralised and democratized digital space beyond the control of big tech. The author acknowledges that the ideal vision of a decentralized and interoperable Metaverse proposed by some will not be achievable. Rather, it is expected that virtual worlds with decentralized governance will coexist alongside those that remain under the control of large multinational corporations.

The theme of decentralisation plays a fundamental role in the discussion of the definitions and characteristics of the Metaverse, as it represents a potential break from the current structure of the web. It does not merely introduce new technologies, such as blockchains and cryptocurrencies, but, more importantly, it entails a radically different concept of web governance.

4. Governance and Technologies in the Transition from Web2 to Web3: The Challenges of Decentralisation

In general, influenced by science fiction imagery and the promises of major tech companies, the Metaverse is primarily conceived as an immersive experience of the web. From this perspective, immersive promises a media experience that deeply involves the user, making them feel like an integral part of the digital world through advanced technologies that stimulate the mind and senses. In the Founder's Letter released by Meta in October 2021, Zuckerberg writes that "the next platform will be even more immersive – an embodied internet where you're in the experience, not just looking at it. We call this the metaverse, and it will touch every product we build. The defining quality of the metaverse will be a feeling of presence – as if you are right there with another person or in another place. Feeling truly present with another person is the ultimate dream of social technology. That is why we are focused on building this"¹⁷. We will revisit the theme of immersivity and the technologies that enable this type of experience.

However, alongside immersivity, another major theme shapes the debate about the Metaverse of the future: decentralisation. This theme is far more controversial, though less well-known to the general public. This is because the evolution that marks the transition from web2, with its social networks, to web3, the Metaverse, becomes problematic for certain interests when it describes a new generation of the internet as «a decentralized internet, as opposed to an internet that's controlled by corporations and governments [...]. Therefore, web3 symbolizes a more

¹⁷ Meta's presentation video also provides interesting insight into this topic, illustrating how the company aims to build the Metaverse: <https://www.facebook.com/facebook/videos/577658430179350/> [last accessed 14 November 2024].

equitable, user-controlled internet, powered largely by token-based economics and blockchain-based interactions and transactions» (Marr 2023:26). According to some, the sign of this radical change in the internet is not only the immersiveness of the experience, but the creation of an open-source, trustless, and permissionless web (Marr 2023). The aim is to overcome the current model of platform society, characterised by the monopoly of the five big tech companies in the web infrastructure and, in particular, in the collection, circulation, and commodification of data. This direction leads to a web whose main characteristics are «openness, decentralisation, and users' full empowerment, enabling them to control and realise the economic value of their data, manage their online identities, and participate in governing the web. Semantic web capabilities allow linking data across webpages, applications, and files. Decentralised technologies and digital twins enable peer-to-peer transactions, transparency, data democracy, and innovation along entire value chains» (EC 2023:1)¹⁸.

The governance dynamics of Web 2.0, encapsulated in the concept of platform society by Dijck, Poell, and de Waal (2019)¹⁹, have long been the subject of criticism and challenges. This model is indeed accused of increasing pervasiveness, accompanied by diminishing transparency and, in some cases, issues related to its legitimacy and legal compliance (see Zuboff 2015²⁰; Barassi 2021²¹). Digital platforms have become new public spaces for communication, sharing, and exchange on the internet, where not only information circulates but also behavioural norms and consumption patterns. These digital environments do not merely facilitate interactions among users; on the contrary, they profoundly influence how people communicate, connect, and build relationships. Platforms pervasively regulate daily practices, from entertainment to education, work, and consumption, thus redefining the dynamics of power and social control (Dijck, Poell, de Wall 2019). What emerges from the analysis by Dijck and colleagues is a society in which flows of social and economic traffic are increasingly channelled through a global ecosystem of online platforms (mostly corporate), driven by algorithms and fueled by data (Dijck, Poell, de Waal 2019:27). This platform ecosystem is currently organised and dominated by a few large corporations that control the main access points to the digital society and key technological services. On the surface, this seems to concern only online activities such as web searches, messaging, social media, content sharing, e-commerce, streaming, and hosting, which are today monopolised by the major tech companies known as the “Big Five” (Meta, Apple, Microsoft, Google—now Alphabet, and Amazon). However, the issue becomes more complex when considering the significant dependence, even within public services, on platform-based systems.

¹⁸ European Commission. (2023). *Communication on “An EU initiative on Web 4.0 and virtual worlds: a head start in the next technological transition”*, 11.7.2023, COM(2023) 442/final, available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/eu-initiative-virtual-worlds-head-start-next-technological-transition>.

¹⁹ Dijck, J., Poell, T., de Waal, M. (2019). Platform society. Valori pubblici e società connessa. [*Platform society. Public values and connected society*]. (Boccia Artieri, G., Marinelli, A. ed.; Marinelli, A., Massa, A., Parisi, S. Tras. It.). Milano: guerini scientifica.

²⁰ Zuboff, S. (2015). Big other: surveillance capitalism and the prospects of an information civilization. *Journal of Information Technology* (2015) 30, 75–89.

²¹ Barassi, V. (2021). I figli dell'algoritmo: Sorvegliati, tracciati e profilati dalla nascita [*The Children of the Algorithm: Monitored, Tracked, and Profiled from Birth*]. Luiss University Press.

For instance, consider the use of Google for data storage and management in schools, where many institutions have adopted Google Classroom for teaching and task organisation. In the healthcare sector, platforms such as Microsoft Azure or Amazon Web Services (AWS) are often used for the secure storage of electronic health records. Additionally, pagoPA, the system for making payments to public administration, relies on private digital platforms that manage transactions and banking data, raising concerns about the security and transparency of citizens' financial information processing.

The primary concern raised by the concentration of power in the hands of the Big Five in the creation and management of the platforms and infrastructures²² on which they rely revolves, first and foremost (though not exclusively), around the centrality of datafication processes in the contemporary global economy. In her book *I Figli dell'Algoritmo. Sorvegliati, tracciati e profilati sin dalla nascita* (The Children of the Algorithm: Monitored, Tracked, and Profiled from Birth), anthropologist Veronica Barassi (2021) outlines a clear picture of how data has become the fundamental currency in the economic system of digital society, highlighting the potential risks to our individual and collective self-determination. Through a critical reflection, Barassi warns of the dangerous consequences that may arise from the control and manipulation of personal data and the role that the Big Five play in this context. The author notes that the development of certain technologies, such as supercomputers and artificial intelligence, has contributed to the «restructuring of daily life, with government entities, educational and healthcare institutions, businesses of all kinds, and many other actors engaged in collecting as much personal data as possible and transforming our everyday behaviours into digital traces» (Barassi, 2021:19, trans. by the author). Within this framework of capitalising on personal data, Zuboff²³ has highlighted the crucial role of technology multinationals in the construction of this new economic model. Google, in particular, discovered in 2002 the «behavioural surplus, or the added value of our data. At the time, digital companies were already collecting vast amounts of personal data to improve their technologies and services. However, Google realised that this data had an additional surplus: it could also be sold to third parties. The value of the behavioural surplus lies in the fact that all collected personal data can be used for predictive analysis or, in other words, to identify behavioural patterns that, theoretically, allow companies not only to interpret users' needs and thus create more targeted advertising, but also to “predict the future”, mitigate risk, and

²² Dijck and colleagues, in their analysis of the platform ecosystem, distinguish between infrastructure platforms and sector-specific platforms. The former, predominantly controlled by the five major tech companies, constitute the foundational technological architecture on which other platforms are built. These infrastructural services include search engines, browsers, data servers, cloud services, email and messaging systems, social networks, identification systems, payment methods, navigation services, and many others. Operating beneath—or rather, alongside—these infrastructure platforms are sector-specific platforms, which focus on particular domains such as information, transportation, education, and healthcare. Unlike infrastructure platforms, sector-specific platforms do not provide the technological underpinnings but deliver targeted services. Nonetheless, nearly all platforms outside the domain of the five big tech companies rely, to varying degrees, on the infrastructural services these dominant players provide (Dijck, Poell, de Waal, 2019).

²³ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power*. PublicAffair.

influence our behaviours» (Barassi 2021:18-19, trans. by the author). All our online social activities, such as posting a message, liking a post, following a user, making a payment or reservation, browsing real estate websites, and so on, are, in fact, also used by platforms to track the demographic, behavioural, and relational profile of users. These seemingly simple interactions feed into complex technological infrastructures that continuously collect and analyse data to connect users with services and targeted advertisements. Platforms transform objects, emotions, and ideas into marketable goods, which are valued through various forms of currency, including attention, data, users, and money.

In this digital context, often considered dystopian and claustrophobic due to the inability to carry out «any action and exchange on the web can only occur through the hyper mediation of a platform that profits from actions and exchanges due to it simply fostering them, by providing them with a codified and regulated form» (Punzi 2025:5)²⁴, it is no coincidence that the principle of decentralisation entrusted to Web3 represents a crucial yet controversial element, far from uncontroversial. In this perspective, the new architecture of digital space should realise the vision of a decentralised internet through blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies, and NFTs.

Blockchain technologies «ensure the security of data records and generate trust without requiring trusted third parties. It is closely related to user-generated content (UGC), such as digital assets that can greatly enrich the Metaverse. For example, NFTs, which are used for trading in the Metaverse, are data units on the blockchain. Defining the ownership of UGC in the Metaverse is a practical challenge, as digital assets can be copied and reproduced. NFTs provide an effective way to prove that UGC is unique and non-fungible. They enable owners of digital content to sell or trade their property via smart contracts in the decentralised crypto space (e.g., using cryptocurrencies)» (Cheng *et al.* 2022). The transition from Web2 to Web3 lies precisely in this different management of data and exchanges, no longer mediated by platforms controlled by large corporations, and in which «only the content producer will be paid for the content produced, and no other platform or person will be able to profit from these applications» (Nalbant, Uyanik 2022:12)²⁵. The decentralised governance of digital spaces via blockchain, including virtual worlds, allows users to participate in decision-making and development without the intervention of central authorities. This form of organisation is defined as Decentralised Autonomous Organisation (DAO), a term that refers «not to a particular type of business model or a particular type of organisation, but a concept that can be used to refer to a wide variety of things. Various authors have pointed out that DAOs could be used to further economic and political decentralisation in ways that may enable a more democratic and participatory form of governance» (Hassan, De Filippi 2021:5-6)²⁶.

²⁴ Punzi, C. (2025). *Notes from Webground. Memory of the Future and Future of Memory*. [In publication].

²⁵ Nalbant, K.; Uyanik, S. (2022). A Look At New Humanity: Metaverse and Metahuman. *International Journal of Computer*, 7(2022).

²⁶ Hassan, S.; De Filippi, P. (2021). Decentralized Autonomous Organization. *Internet Policy Review. Journal on Internet regulation*, 10(2), 2-10.

In conclusion, as noted by several authors (Chang *et. al.* 2022; Punzi, 2025; Barassi 2019), the transition from Web2 to Web3 is not the only digital transformation that has occurred in the name of decentralisation, intending to increasingly democratise media, information, communication, and online exchange. This imperative also characterised the shift from traditional media (more commonly known as mass media) to social media. In this context, the innovations introduced by digital media have brought a wave of cyber-optimism within a digital space made up of virtual communities, permanent and shared access to knowledge, and technodemocracy driven by digital egalitarianism and expressive libertarianism, which sometimes seems determined by the very nature of network technology and its properties (Bentivenga, Boccia Artieri 2019)²⁷. However, as we have seen, despite the noble intentions embedded in the genesis of the platformisation of the internet, aimed at freeing the media from the centralised dominance of newspapers and television, it must also be acknowledged that this project was subsumed and transformed by Silicon Valley's managers (Punzi 2025).

It remains to be asked, then, at what stage the current development and implementation of the Metaverse stands. Does it truly represent a revolution of the web, or is it already experiencing processes of subsumption by the Big Five? The analysis of the enabling technologies helps guide us in this observation.

5. Enabling Technologies

In the landscape of some of the current definitions of the Metaverse (see section 3), it emerges that the ongoing debate on the topic develops along two main directions. On the one hand, some approaches emphasise the social aspects and the relationships that the Metaverse is already influencing or may induce within the context of digital societies. On the other, some perspectives focus more on the enabling technologies, highlighting their structural role. In the previous section, we described and discussed the digital models that organise social, economic, political, and cultural activities within which the Metaverse is situated (see section 4). At this point, it is particularly relevant to delve into the technologies and IT infrastructures currently available, examining how they intertwine with and shape the core definitions and constitutive characteristics of the Metaverse.

The most interesting aspect to explore in this regard is not so much the technical characteristics of the devices or technologies themselves but the ability to grasp the values and principles that these technologies transmit and incorporate. In agreement with critics of the Value-Neutrality Thesis, which posits the political and moral neutrality of technology, our reflection supports the

²⁷ Bentivenga, S.; Boccia Artieri, G. (2019). *Le teorie della comunicazione di massa e le sfide del digitale [Mass Communication Theories and the Challenges of the Digital Era]*. Editori Laterza.

idea that «technological artefacts are part of the normative moral and political order rather than external to it» (Miller 2020:2). In this sense, even when the definition of the Metaverse is framed within a primarily technical and technological discourse, it cannot be ascribed intrinsic neutrality. This is because every action in the digital context is necessarily mediated by the operational possibilities that the different technologies make available. These technologies not only shape the scope of what can be done but also embed specific affordances, constraints, and design logic that guide and, in many cases, subtly dictate user behaviour. For instance, the structure of a platform, the type of data it collects, and the way it processes interactions all influence how users engage with digital spaces. This dynamic creates a feedback loop where technological features both enable and limit actions, reinforcing certain patterns of behaviour while discouraging others. As a result, the architecture of these technologies actively participates in constructing the norms, practices, and expectations within the digital environment, fundamentally altering the way users navigate and experience the virtual world. In summary, whenever we observe the technologies and devices that enable the use of the Metaverse, it is important to bear in mind that all the knowledge embedded in them inherently carries values, which are inevitably transmitted (Miller 2020)²⁸.

The definition proposed by Stylianos Mystakidis (2022)²⁹ provides a comprehensive outline of the technologies enabling the Metaverse in its most contemporary form. The author describes the Metaverse as «the post-reality universe, a perpetual and persistent multiuser environment merging physical reality with digital virtuality. It is based on the convergence of technologies that enable *multisensory interactions* with virtual environments, digital objects, and people, such as *virtual reality* (VR) and *augmented reality* (AR). Hence, the Metaverse is an interconnected web of social, networked *immersive* environments in *persistent* multiuser platforms. It enables seamless embodied user communication in *real-time and dynamic interactions* with digital artefacts. Its first iteration was a web of virtual worlds where *avatars* were able to teleport among them. The contemporary iteration of the Metaverse features social, immersive VR platforms compatible with massively multiplayer online video games, open game worlds, and AR collaborative spaces» (Mystakidis 2022:486, emphasis added).

Here are some key definitions that help to understand Mystakidis' proposal and, consequently, the fundamental technological characteristics that should enable the Metaverse of the future. As discussed in previous sections, immersiveness is a key attribute of the Metaverse. It describes the quality of the experience offered by virtual worlds, which consists of two main components: the perception of presence on the web, which transforms the experience from an interaction "in front of the screen" to one of being "inside the web", and the sensory dimension, which enriches the interaction through stimuli perceptible by the senses. Both characteristics, which mediate the different degrees of immersion, depend on the technologies used.

²⁸ Miller, B. (2020). Is Technology Value-Neutral?. In *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 1-28

²⁹ Mystakidis, S. (2022). Metaverse. In *Encyclopedia*, 2022 (2), 486-497.

Synchronicity is another crucial factor that enables an immersive virtual experience. It refers to the ability of virtual environments to allow communication and interaction between users in real time, creating a sense of co-presence that makes the experience even more engaging and realistic.

Persistence refers to the fact that virtual worlds continue to evolve even when users are not actively connected, and the effects of these changes are perceived by users when they return online.

Three-dimensionality is the ability to experience user interaction in 3D virtual environments simulated by computers, in the case of Virtual Reality (VR), or through interaction with three-dimensional virtual objects created by computers, as seen in Augmented Reality (AR) or Mixed Reality (MR). Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, and Mixed Reality represent the key gateways to the Metaverse. Virtual Reality (VR) immerses users in a virtual world. Augmented Reality (AR) enables digital twins in the Metaverse to be overlaid onto physical objects, effectively linking the Metaverse with the physical world. Mixed Reality (MR) allows users to interact with virtual objects, creating more connections and collaborative relationships between the physical world, the virtual space, and the users (Cheng *et al.* 2022).

Interoperability is defined as the ability to seamlessly use identities, avatars, data, virtual assets, experiences, or environments and the associated rights across platforms and networks (Di Porto, Fòa, Ennis 2024). For many, interoperability is a fundamental element for the true realisation of the Metaverse. On this topic, Matthew Ball asserts that the Metaverse offers unprecedented interoperability, i.e. users have to be able to take their avatars and goods from one place in the Metaverse to another, no matter who runs that particular part of it (Ball 2020).

Among the Big Five companies that are heavily investing in the Metaverse and the development of enabling hardware technologies, Meta undoubtedly stands out. The company is focusing its efforts on immersive platforms like Horizon Worlds and the development of VR hardware devices such as the Quest glasses, aiming to transform the digital landscape and enhance social experiences. Microsoft is also aiming to offer mixed reality solutions for businesses through its Mesh platform and by integrating Metaverse functionalities into Teams for virtual meetings and collaborations between physical and digital environments. Apple is entering the Metaverse with its Vision Pro, a device that integrates augmented and virtual reality to create immersive experiences between the physical and digital worlds. Alongside these tech giants, platforms like Roblox, one of the most popular for user-generated content, especially among younger users, are significant. Epic Games, which has heavily invested in the Metaverse, uses the Unreal engine to create dynamic 3D environments for gaming and social interactions. Lastly, Nvidia's Omniverse platform allows the creation of 3D virtual worlds and is used in sectors such as video games, architecture, and design. Thanks to the power of its graphics cards and AI-based technologies, Nvidia plays a key role in the development of technologies for the Metaverse.

In Italy, the Public Administration is beginning to explore the use of the Metaverse, although it is still in the experimental phase. For instance, the CSI Piemonte Consortium is testing new methods of interaction with citizens in the Metaverse, designing virtual spaces where young people can participate in meetings and receive support.